

METHODOLOGY OF COURSE ORGANIZATION IN THE NATIONAL VIRTUAL EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT

Delov T.E.

Tashkent University of Information Technologies named after Muhammad al-Khorazmiy, Associate Professor V.V. Uzbekistan

dilov_t_e@mail.ru

Currently, virtual reality technology has become a new educational tool for the development of education. Traditional education only provides students with knowledge, now virtual reality technology can be used to help students create a vivid learning environment so that students can experience it in real life. Compared with passive infusion, compared with passive infusion, the sense of memory enhancement, using virtual reality technology, the implementation of autonomous learning can allow the student to accept, it is easier to stimulate students' interest in learning. a virtual world about topics that help students learn better using virtual reality technologies.

In particular, significant work is being done on the use of virtual education in the higher education system of Uzbekistan. As an example, we can take the innovative project work No. IL-4721071198 entitled "Creating a national virtual university of information technologies based on 3D technologies". This project is intended for 2022-2023, and it is planned to carry out large-scale works within the framework of the project.

Virtual Academy offers a qualitatively new approach to learning in virtual worlds.

Virtual worlds provide excellent opportunities for effective distance and online learning by supporting groups or communities that bring together subject matter experts, teachers, and students from different countries or locations. Thus, the development of new collaborative e-learning approaches is facilitated.

Virtual Academy is a three-dimensional multi-user educational platform that allows you to conduct training courses, meetings, presentations, trainings for groups from one to several dozen users at the same time and provides services in which you can participate.

The use of the vAcademia program is effective in organizing virtual education. After enrolling in this program, it will be possible to participate in the classes of scientists from all over the world by organizing an optional course on any subject.

One of the main partners of the work carried out within the framework of the project, quality work is being organized together with the head of the Multimedia System Laboratory, Associate Professor Mikhail N. Morozov. The many tutorials they have created using vAcademia are a good resource for students and freelancers alike. We also organize virtual classes in Uzbek using the vAcademia program as part of the project.

First of all, we will register on the website vacademia.uz and organize the course. This process continues with entering information about the course.

A new course or subject is created from the "teaching" section in the menu bar provided in the program.

Figure 1. Enter information about our course

Here we enter information about our course, create a lesson schedule and invite students or listeners to our course.

Mavzu	Tavsif	Vaqt	Sana	boshqaruv
1. Tezis yozish qoidalari	tezis yozish qoidalari yoritiladi	12:00	Дс, 09 Қаңт 2023	↓ ↑ ✎ ✕
2. Maqola yozish qoidalari	Maqola yozish qoidalari yoritiladi	13:50	Сб, 28 Қаңт 2023	↓ ↑ ✎ ✕
3. Maqolalarni nashr ettirish ...	Maqolalarni chop ettirish talablari y...	10:30	Жм, 27 Қаңт 2023	↓ ↑ ✎ ✕
4. DGU olish talablari	EHM uchun mualliflik guvohnomalari ol...	12:30	Дс, 09 Қаңт 2023	↓ ↑ ✎ ✕

Figure 2. Preparation of the lesson schedule

When creating a course in the national virtual system of [Vacademia.uz](http://vacademia.uz), it is necessary to download the vacademia.uz program after registering on the site. Because in the organization of the main lessons, objects in 3D view are implemented in the program installed on the computer. The login and password registered on Vacademia.uz must be the same as the login password in the program installed on the computer.

The user representation in vAcademia is a three-dimensional character - an avatar, which has a unique customizable appearance.

Avatar selection is done during registration on the site. In the future, we can change the appearance using the avatar editor.

Tools for working with 3D objects are grouped under the following tabs:

Objects - for placing objects

Landscape - saving and restoring the placement of objects in a location.

Bots - for hosting computer characters-bots.

Scripts - for programming the behavior of three-dimensional objects in the vJS language.

When organizing a lesson, it is necessary to equip the auditorium.

Our lesson is about the stages of writing an article, based on the unique laws of writing articles and theses, the formation and development of competencies among the participants of the interaction in the educational process is mainly based on the various educational and educational activities of students. It was found that it occurs as a result of independent work with education. and methodical manuals (electronic textbooks, interactive educational programs, electronic knowledge base), in addition, when using communication networks (Internet), this is a constant enrichment of the experience of creative activity to a greater extent, a mechanism of self-management helps to form.

Virtual worlds also have different technological requirements. They can be accessed via a standard web browser by installing a plug-in (if they don't have full 3D graphics), or if they have a full 3D world, the user will need to install the appropriate computer hardware and a standalone software client (app). Most advanced virtual worlds also require a broadband internet connection on the user side.

Figure 3. Conducting the lesson process

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The analysis of the reviewed data shows that the participants of the experimental group were first used in traditional education, and then conducted training in the virtual world. By the end of the lesson, students' abstract questions about the organization of training in the virtual world decreased significantly. Organizing courses and planning lessons in a virtual system is a really clear, suggested activity.

References:

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